

THE ROLE OF LATIN IN THE MODERN MEDICINE

F.Q. Axmedova

F.A. Qandova

Bukhara Institute of Innovative Medicine

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The Latin language continues to be an important cultural phenomenon in the modern world. Without this seemingly "dead language" it is impossible to imagine many areas of human activity. In this regard, it is appropriate to recall the statement of the author of the textbook "The Latin Language and Introduction to Ancient Culture" A.V. languages, becoming the basis for some (Italian, Spanish, French, Portuguese, Romanian, Moldavian and some others) and giving hundreds, thousands of words and terms to other languages ... and the Russian language has not escaped this influence. If you look closely, it turns out that the scope of Latin is very wide and has a significant variety.

Scientific terminology, therefore, belongs to the field of international vocabulary, largely built on the basis of the Latin language and its forms. This vocabulary should be equally understandable to educated people all over the world. Of course, much of the medical or scientific terminology is technical and therefore known to few. But in the international vocabulary there is the most common layer, which consists of the most common words, mainly of social or political significance, which should be known and understood by everyone. This includes such words borrowed from the Latin language (or formed using its forms) as humanism, republic, dictatorship, forum, university, international, association, applicant, assistant, associate professor, internship, student, scholarship, seminar, professor, lecture, laboratory assistant and others [1,3,5,6]. Of course, a large part of the international vocabulary is borrowed from the Greek language and from the main modern languages. In addition, it must be borne in mind that it is truly international only for those people who speak a language that uses such vocabulary. In the main modern languages, including Russian, internationalisms make up up to 10% of the vocabulary. Scientists estimate that out of the 20,000 most common words in the English language, about 10,400 are Latin origin, about 220 - Greek and only 5400 - Anglo-Saxon.

Thus, Latin is the main language of the Catholic religion and is used in medicine to form anatomical, clinical and pharmaceutical terms. The role of the Latin language in the formation of Western European languages and in the enrichment of the Russian language with borrowed words, winged and professional expressions is enormous. Therefore it is clear that the study of the Latin language, maintaining a high level of knowledge in this area is a very urgent task of modern education.

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